

Applying the Milieus–Oriented Concept in a Church Context: Prospects and Challenges

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ABSTRACT: During the recent decades, within the process of individualization of a society, there have been various attempts within the spectrum of social sciences to materialize the differentiated and segmented image of a society. Consequently, modern research of the milieus deals with the study of different social “worlds”, characterized by a pattern of common values, communication and experience. The holistic, milieu-oriented concept found resonance within Church activity, providing a valuable approach to the emerging new perspectives. Yet, its adoption signals not only opportunities, but also challenges. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to reflect upon the possibilities and limits of applying the concept of social milieus to the Church, and to analyze it in a critical manner; highlighting, at the same time, its potential.

KEY WORDS: milieus, Church, liturgy, mission potential, challenges

Today, it is known and accepted that modern western society is highly fragmented from a social point of view. The extent to which this affects and causes changes in the church—was the topic of many research studies over the past 10 years. These research studies are trying to include the image of the society in a manner as holistic as possible. This article refers to such studies, which—due to the milieu oriented concept—threw an ample “sociologic look” on to the church.¹ However the debate will take place in the theological context

addressing the current church reform intention. Often because they try to overcome the “crisis” of the church, manifested by reduced visitor numbers for the divine services, decreased finance and public attention. To what extent the holistic sociological orientation is useful and a successful approach within the church context—this is the subject of the discussion.

Milieus-Oriented Concept in Society and Church

What are *milieus*? Social sciences have described social inequality in the past through categories of class or social blanket. The differentiated typology of social milieus appeared since 1987 on the basis of many qualitative studies representative. Ulrich Beck’s theory of individualization does not define the individual through the innate belonging to a social class. On the contrary, the individual can and must discover and create himself, fact for which he assumes the responsibility alone.² In the 1990s the milieu theory reaches the center of attention through the publication of Gerhard Schulzes, “Consumer Society,” when theory about society becomes a *theory about milieus*.

Milieu theory starts from the premise that our society is fragmented and “breaks” in milieus and sub-milieus. Milieus are models or social constructs through which social reality is tried to be described. Milieus are recognized by the fact that they own common patterns of values, communication and experience as well as due to “an intense internal communication.”³ Milieus are self-contained worlds, groups of people with the same aspirations, who feel connected to each other by attitudes, mode of communication, thinking, and mode of action, education level or similar material state. Unlike milieu, mentalities (premodern, modern, and postmodern) are unreflected groups attitudes yet sustainable, feelings or patterns of action.⁴

Milieus differentiation, as life worlds is also valid for the church with its forms: as a local church, as a group initiative, or regional church.⁵ Following the application of various survey instruments in the church, it resulted that local churches are determined by a few dominant milieus. Consequently church attracts only people who

belong to those milieus or have intentions of social ascent; thus church services are not an offer “for all”—as was thought before.⁶

In a group of similar people—who think, talk and live alike—the individual finds peace in a time of disorientation and identity, created by separating from the other milieus. For these and generally human communities are defined inside a society just by separating from the other. This relationship is certainly critical because the auto recruiting mechanism dominates in a group: one group only attracts people that fit it.⁷ At the same time it must not be forgotten that religious forms in turn influence the individual habitus and thus the formation of a milieu. This occurs because faith is not conceivable without a social form.

Since 1999 publications have appeared about the relationship between different milieus and the church, particularly the studies of M. Vester, from the “Working group in the social interdisciplinary structure research.” This was followed by the study in the evangelical Protestant church (Germany) of Frederike Benthaus-Apel “Church in the diversity of its features,” which has developed a typology of lifestyles with 6 types.⁸ According to the EKD study we can see “which society milieus are represented in the church, which needs, interest and aesthetic preferences they [church members] bring with them and which church offers are satisfied.”⁹ Frederike Benthaus-Apel points out that there is a clear causality “between social milieu, lifestyle, commitment and participation of the Christian religion.”¹⁰

In 2005 he followed an extensive study in the Catholic Church in Germany- based on socio-scientific typology Sinus (with 10 milieus), aiming to see, to what extent differentiation of society is reflected in the church, and to which milieu church it truly arrives. The effect of those results can be felt until today: even if there are church members in all milieus, though there are only certain types of milieus, who actively participate in church life. Church reaches through its offers to people from following milieus: high cultural, tradition oriented or sociable- oriented to tradition, in part and high-cultural-modern. From these milieus the church recruits its “public”, though the seniors’ age is overrepresented in these milieus.¹¹ Generally the Church is strong in regions where a premodern mentality dominates;

and weak where postmodern orientation dominates or at the bottom of society.¹²

These surprising results led to further taking the concept-oriented milieu, which through various research tools (like SINUS) made its way into the church in order to deliver valuable information. They combine a subjective perspective of life with objective characteristics in order to achieve a more complete overview. That is because only a holistic description of the individual leads to a real description of everyday's life. Thus, the SINUS project gather a lot of information about individuals, such as: the social status, their own philosophy of life, image about society, attitude towards labor, towards marriage, family and leisure, aspirations and patterns, lifestyle, aesthetics, etc.¹³

Thus it became clear that church parishioners who come from different types of milieus are very different in their expectations and image on: the liturgical service, sermon form and content, understanding of the faith, the Bible, theology, art and motivation.¹⁴ This fact has led simultaneously to the critical analysis of the theory of individualism, which is in danger of neglect, not perceiving the existing similarities in social groups or milieus.¹⁵

The process of social differentiation lingers on, like postmodernism, while the church clientele, as the traditional-conservatives group shrinks more and more. There are almost no milieus as a role model for others. Most people have their own system of values, which goes without saying and does not need the church as mediator of values.¹⁶ In this framework, to what extent can the holistic milieus oriented concept to offer a solution for the church?

Prospects and Potential Applications of the Holistic Milieus-Oriented Concept in the Church

Thesis 1: The holistic milieus oriented concept helps develop the perception vis-a vis the current fragmentation of society and consequently the church. Even if the church parishioners are found in all groups of milieu, yet only a minor part answers the church's offers. Same in the activity of a normal community not all milieus

are represented. I have already mentioned that the church is limited to 2-3 milieus: traditional group, conservative group and middle civil group.¹⁷ In this sense the milieu concept is a “perceptual aid” essential,¹⁸ as it helps the church to gain back a sense of reality necessary in contextualizing the Gospel in a postmodern society and in view of an effective action.¹⁹

Meanwhile milieus oriented perspective offers release from the pressure created against the church, to achieve people from all walks of life. It’s possible some other milieus to discover and highlight other aspects of the Gospel. The fact of discovering different aspects of faith reflected by different milieus in a diversity sense - constitutes another advantage related to this concept.²⁰ Through a Christian opening towards people from other milieus it can be achieved both a widening of the spiritual horizon and an intensification of community fellowship.

Thesis 2: The holistic milieus oriented concept offers a clear and open perspective on the church’s efficiency in society—mission. In this regard G. Werner said: “The question of the church’s milieu dependence is from a theological point of view nothing less than the question regarding the mission. . . . The incarnation takes place in the milieu.”²¹ In this context it becomes obvious that the church, before the advertising industry appeared, has already adapted to different categories of people: elderly, youth, women, men. Today society is much more differentiated, so that the *age* criterion is no longer convincing. People who have a similar age may still belong from a cultural point of view to entirely different worlds. Today’s youth is no longer only addressed through a single “youth activity”; just as little the senior category through the “50+” project. For the milieu research just proves very clearly that these age groups are very heterogeneous. Thus the milieu oriented concept further provides an optimization proposal.²²

For the mission does not mean giving away “a container with theory, called the Gospel”. (H. Hempelmann) Following the model of Jesus of Nazareth, who could not and did not want other to show His love for man by other than becoming a man among men - and so the mission has to descend deeper and seek fellowship with people

from other milieus, to discover with them the Gospel message and how the fragmented human community can recover and take the form of the church. The concept of milieu here provides support in identifying both the connecting bridges as well as the obstacles. Though the Gospel's message is attractive, it is possible that due to an inappropriate form or language, unknown, due to a manner insensible towards milieu to lead to refusal. It is precisely the mission's space where the people need to be approached closer to their understanding.²³

Thesis 3: The holistic milieus oriented concept offers valuable impulse in local and inter-regional church organization. In principle each representative denomination's local community can be considered a "milieu church", meaning it holds a certain style and way of being, thus attracting only a certain category of people. This should not be necessarily seen as negative because these churches operate according to the motto: "we have success with this style!"²⁴ The local community cannot and must not exceed every milieu limit.

They is mentioned a 3-way choice in treating the milieu reality. *First* there is the possibility that each community to "specialize" in a milieu profile which to promote further. But as a consequence, the outlook communities will be removed so much from one another, that prejudices and alienation will appear and threaten the unity of the church. *A second* possibility would be for the church to offer a new language of "faith" to a milieu. Parishioners should then give up their original milieu and to take in the new one. So then the Church will create its special and specific milieu. This possibility is often seen in the Neo-protestant churches which develop at the same time.²⁵

Since the 2nd path is not compatible with the major denominations, it advocates for one last option: a church that unites Milieus between them. We have seen that it is not possible for communities - due to their cultural specificity - to go beyond the limits of other Milieus or produce offers for all Milieus. Therefore a regional cooperation makes sense as well as a pluralization of forms in community life. This involves close collaboration at the middle administrative level, in order to achieve a complex missionary plan. Through specialization and / or communities' cooperation between

them it becomes possible to address many Milieus in the region, as well as making specific offers and religious spaces.²⁶ In this context we see 5 project directions: to build on what it is, church growth, church image, ecumenical interconnection or deacon orientation.²⁷

Thesis 4: The holistic milieus oriented concept provides important prognostic information regarding the future of the Church. Various research studies related to the milieus oriented concept track targets that are indispensable for the future development and management of the church. For example it is important to understand how social transition unfolds and in what manner the church can adapt to it. On the other hand the medial reception mode of church offers in different milieus can reveal important details for an efficient medial transmission of the Gospel. In addition the church may obtain due to the milieu oriented concept valuable information on important religious issues for parishioners or about the church connection or separation factors.²⁸

Even the question—*whom does the Church address, and whom does it not?*—requires a regular update process. Milieu regional studies may also indicate the milieu changes, milieu concentrations or reductions in a particular geographic region, which is an aid in long-term planning of missionary activity.²⁹

Thesis 5: The holistic milieus oriented concept also offers practical-analytical instruments in pastoral activity. First the milieus oriented concept provides practical tools for *analysis*, which can be used in awareness of differences in mentality (clarification of milieu), regarding the spread of milieus across the church district (the location of the milieu), in terms of preparing offers tailored to target groups (focus of milieu), and in terms of openness to unknown milieus (expanding of milieu). In addition these practical tools make it possible to analyze the profile of the local community, which may lead to a fair distribution of the opportunities for participation in the liturgical service.³⁰

The milieus oriented concept's instruments find their use in the service of *pastoral* related tasks as: planning of the staff, causalities, behavior towards parishioners estranged from the Church as well

in decision-making at the middle management administrative level regarding counseling and community development, conflict mediation, diaconate work, youth work or in regional cooperation.³¹

Challenges in Applying the Holistic Milieus-Oriented Concept in the Church Context

Thesis 1: The holistic milieus oriented concept requires a review of the role of the church in society, because the Gospel belongs to all people. A church linked to certain social groups has a repelling effect on the others. Many people are kept at a distance from all religious forms and offers not because of lack of openness or interest in the faith, but because of milieu cultural barriers. The more the religious activity identifies with pre-modern or traditional forms of milieu, the more the church will be associated with this lifestyle. The effect of rejection of some completely unknown mentalities is not neutral. The more a form of milieu is farthest from their own the stronger is the effect of alienation and rejection.³² Social shutdown leads to rejection, social exclusion, which massively prevents the missionary efforts. Without overcoming cultural boundaries it is not possible to open the Gospel to people. Cultural contextualization involves opening but also risks at the same time.

Yet it is necessary for the church to ask the question: to what to turn its intentions or must attract people? They all have different religious attitudes and perceptions. How they react is a matter of theological position.³³ Does the pre-modern mentality correspond to the traditional-conservative Christian one? Does it make sense only servicing this social category? Or is it possible to also adapt the Gospel in the modern or postmodern context?³⁴ This is a challenge which the Church cannot turn away from.

Thesis 2: The holistic milieus oriented concept is argued in the market economy system, orienting itself by supply and demand. But contextualization of the Gospel does not imply a pure adaptation or only satisfaction of the needs. The Church must speak not by the will of the people, because the Gospel is not a commodity product, as

the Apostle Paul says, “For we do not corrupt the Word of God as do some.” (2 Cor. 2:17) Michael Ebertz talks about adaptation (from the 2nd Council of Vatican) and distinguishes between conformism, external coordination, opportunism, flattery, etc.³⁵ And G. Wegner warns against a simple orientation towards the milieu, which he defines as treason to the Gospel. It takes a spiritual penetration of the milieu perspective; otherwise only the consumer market will extend.³⁶

It must not be forgotten that a sociological model does not present a whole or the reality, but just a look of it from a certain perspective. The milieu oriented concept owns such a perspective, its goal bring a closer understanding of society.³⁷ Sociological structure models are really just tools to aid in the analysis, reflection and in preventing or detecting deficits.³⁸ It is our duty to judge, moderate, to deduce consequences. The role of the milieu oriented concept is not to define what the church must or must not be. This is a theological task not a sociological one, that requires theological viewpoints in formulating consequences.³⁹

Thesis 3: The holistic milieu oriented concept as “aid perception” is not a panacea. Social-scientific instruments, such as the Sinus or MICROM-GEO-Milieus are not a panacea, especially in solving the problems of the church, but only a instrument.⁴⁰ They do not replace human needs necessary for detachment from a milieu and involvement in an entirely different one. But who does not widens his horizons that will not discover anything new.⁴¹ In this context it is about the milieu oriented concept’s limits:

* The idea - that with more diligence any milieu limit can be overcome and the communities will be welcoming for anyone - is an illusion.

* The individual is not just the representative of a milieu. Perspective on milieu catches only the social differences. But life contains fundamental human issues that are common to all, even if the way of expression is milieu specific.⁴²

* Sinus milieu table - designed for marketing purposes - does not include all the population; from a church point of view it may even be seen a major deficit: e.g. immigrants are only partially considered.

In this context it is recommended in the church evaluation from a social structure point of view, to track both the processes of exclusion and inclusion as well as typical phenomena and the individual ones.⁴³

Thesis 4: Milieus segmentation and differentiation constitutes a challenge for church unity that must be defined beyond Milieus. It requires a clear definition of the church, in order to understand its role. If a community goes down a road together then it needs to agree on a common target. But precisely here lies the challenge on the unity because there are a lot of conceptions about it. We are different, and yet we are all Christians; but what binds us? Where and how is this done? Some see unity in the homogeneous character of a group: similar aesthetic tastes, similar fellowship style, same meaning in life, same aspirations and same detestable things. Others see unity in the common sinful condition and in the universal offer of the redemption plan, aspect which exceeds the allegiance to a milieu.⁴⁴ Determining the unity domain in the church remains a challenge not only on the theological level but also practically.

Thesis 5: The holistic milieus oriented concept may overburden local community. The feeling and pressure to provide programs for 10 milieus can overwhelm and create stress to the local community. In addition we add the question of resources: in the church we are dealing with volunteers, which cannot be had forever. The additive system - meaning more and more, better quality, more differentiated, more intense, more personal and individual - no longer works.⁴⁵ This situation imposes the need to formulate appropriate questions that generate answers which cause no extra burdens, but instead produce a decongesting of the situation.⁴⁶

Such appropriate questions might be such as: in which areas are my talents and where are the talents of others? Is there a disposition to delegate tasks according to individual gifts and talents? How can they be promoted? Is there encouragement for regional cooperation, which can make available new resources and generate relaxation and synergy effects?⁴⁷

Concluding Reflections

Until mid 20th century life in Western society has been marked by clarity, continuity and the static, thus a parish image of the church was welcome. But today, due to social fragmentation, religious communities have become rather groups of similar people. Now the church needs integrative offers, to approach people in their specific life environments. Perhaps reflecting on the holistic future prospects of the church—as a combination of milieu communities—would be a beneficial option.⁴⁸

In the set of countless theological discussions on options for reform, it must be necessary to bring to light some objective distinctions between theology and sociology. The sociological eye on the results related to social milieus proves that the situation is more complex than it seems at first glance. For on the one hand there is evidence of weakening the relationship with the church, and on the other hand, the studies confirm the interest in religious beliefs and the possibilities of approach. The fact is that the Church must balance two goals: on the one hand—developing and maintaining their own identity, and on the other hand: reaction to the differentiating and the changing of society, distinction as well as integration.⁴⁹

Even if contextualizing the Gospel is important in holistic reaching the people staying away from the church, though one should not lose sight of the fact as a compelling and enthusiastic testimony of faith, usually has a positive effect despite milieu barriers.⁵⁰ Finally, above the professionalism and cultural orientation is the love for people: “And if I have not love, I am nothing” (1 Cor. 13.2). Without developing a spiritual perspective the application of the milieus oriented concept in religious context will never reach its possible target.

There will always be differences of milieu and yet the church parishioners—even if they don’t have too much in common—“practice the same things together and with each other.”⁵¹ Before God all the differences of milieu are cancelled. In liturgical acts, e.g. the Last Supper, it becomes clear that the church transcends the order imposed by milieus. So the church can harness the diversity

and at same time can provide direction and hope.⁵² A Church which continuously allows itself to be recreated and shaped by God—*ecclesia semper reformanda*—can only profit from the challenges of the holistic milieus oriented concept,⁵³ and also at the same time to achieve a balanced balancing between individuality and community.

NOTES

¹ See Bremer Vögele, Helmut Wolfgang, Michael Vester, *Soziale Milieus und Kirche*, Würzburg: Ergon Verlag, 2002.

² Ulrich Beck, *Risikogesellschaft*. Frankfurt an Main, 1986.

³ Michael N. Ebertz, „Anschlüsse gesucht. Ergebnisse einer neuen Milieu-Studie zu den Katholiken in Deutschland, in *Herder-Korrespondenz* 80 (2006): 174.

⁴ Heinzpeter Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu. Wie Sinusstudien der Kirche helfen können, Menschen zu erreichen*. 2. erweiterte (Auflage, Brunnen Verlag, Gießen, 2013), 35–36.

⁵ Wolfgang Huber, *Kirche*. 1. (Stuttgart; Berlin: Aufl., Kreuz-Verlag, 1979), 47ff.

⁶ Heinzpeter Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu. Die Sinus-Kirchenstudie „Evangelisch in Baden und Württemberg. Ergebnisse und Impulse für den Gottesdienst.“* BrunnenVerlag, Gießen, 2013), 42–43.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 74–75.

⁸ Claudia Schulz, Eberhard Hauschild, and Eike Kohler, *Milieus Praktisch II. Konkretionen für Helfendes Handeln in Kirche und Diakonie* (Göttingen, 2010), 43–44.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 205.; See also, Friederike Benthaus-Apel, „Lebensstile und Kirchenmitgliedschaft. Zur Differenzierung der ‚treuen Kirchenfernen,“ in Kirchenamt der EKD (Eds.): *Kirche –Horizont und Lebensrahmen. Weltsichten, Kirchenbindung. Vierte EKD-Erhebung über Kirchenmitgliedschaft*. Hannover, 2003. Friederike Benthaus-Apel, „Lebensstilspezifische Zugänge zur Kirchenmitgliedschaft“ in Huber Wolfgang (Ed.), *Kirche in der Vielfalt der Lebenszüge. Die vierte EKD-Erhebung über Kirchenmitgliedschaft*, Gütersloh, 2006; Michael Vester, Peter von Oertzen et. al. *Soziale Milieus im gesellschaftlichen Strukturwandel*, Frankfurt a. Main, 2001.

¹¹ See Schulz cit. in Uta Pohl-Patalong, „Kommentar ‚Lebensstile‘ und Kirche,“ in: Huber Wolfgang et.al. (Ed.): *Kirche in der Vielfalt der Lebensbezüge. Die vierte EKD-Erhebung über Kirchenmitgliedschaft*. (Gütersloh, 2006), 274ff.

¹² Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu*, 15.

¹³ Cf. www.Praxisinstitut.de (Last visited on, August 11, 2016)

¹⁴ Claudia Schulz, Eberhard Hauschild, and Eike Kohler, *Milieus praktisch II. Konkretionen für helfendes Handeln in Kirche und Diakonie* (Göttingen, 2010), 282ff.

¹⁵ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 35.

- ¹⁶ Ibid., 67ff.
- ¹⁷ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 47; Comp. Ingrid Eilers, Kurse zum Glauben für verschiedene Sinus-Milieus, in: Arbeitsgemeinschaft Missionarische Dienste (Ed.), *Erwachsen glauben. Missionarische Bildungsangebote. Grundlagen-Kontexte-Praxis* (Gütersloh, 2011), 81ff.
- ¹⁸ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 13ff.; 69.
- ¹⁹ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 91ff.; comp. Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 247.
- ²⁰ Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu*, 43. Comp. Ibid., 97–98.
- ²¹ Wegner 2000, 53-70.
- ²² Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu*, 95.
- ²³ Ibid., 49ff.
- ²⁴ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 250; Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu*, 62–63.
- ²⁵ Jörg Stolz et.al., *Phänomen Freikirchen. Analysen eines wettbewerbsstarken Milieus*. Bd.5 (Zürich: Pano Verlag, 2014), 25ff.; comp. Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, 246.
- ²⁶ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 98–99.
- ²⁷ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 250ff.
- ²⁸ Hempelmann, *Kirche im Mileu*, 20–21.
- ²⁹ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, 232ff; Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 103.
- ³⁰ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 103–105.
- ³¹ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, 237ff.; comp. Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 105ff.
- ³² Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 42.
- ³³ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 130; Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 261.
- ³⁴ Martin Lätzel, „Jedem das Seine?“ in *Pastorallblatt für die Diözesen*. Aachen, Berlin Essen, Hildesheim, Köln, Osnabrück (2007): 181–185, here 183.
- ³⁵ Michael N. Ebertz, „Anschlüsse gesucht. Ergebnisse einer neuen Milieu-Studie zu den Katholiken in Deutschland,“ in: *Herder-Korrespondenz* 80 (2006): 173-177, here 176ff.
- ³⁶ Gerhard Wegner, „Potentiale provozieren.Über die Selbstwirksamkeit des Glaubens und seine Verkleisterung,“ in Pilipp Ehlhaus, Christian Hennecke (Eds.) *Gottes Sehnsucht in der Stadt. Auf der Suche nach Gemeinden für Morgen* (Würzburg: 2011), 121-144.
- ³⁷ Wolfgang Vögele, Helmut Bremer, Michael Vester, *Soziale Milieus und Kirche*. (Würzburg: Ergon Verlag, 2002), 121–131.
- ³⁸ Comp. Vögele et.al. 2002, 22ff.
- ³⁹ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 109.
- ⁴⁰ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, Ibid., 13ff.; Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 101.
- ⁴¹ Hempelmann, *Gott im Mileu*, 135.
- ⁴² Comp. Joachim Wanke, „Was uns die Sinus-Milieu-Studie über die Kirche und ihre Pastoral sagen kann – und was nicht. Anfragen und Anregungen an Mileu-Studie und Kirche,“ in *Lebendige Seelsorge* 57 (2006): 242–246.
- ⁴³ Rudolf Tippelt, et.al., „Weiterbildung und soziale Mileus in Deutschland,“ in Bd.3: *Mileumarketing implementieren*. (Bielefeld. 2008), 88–95.

⁴⁴ Wolfgang Huber, *Soziale Milieus und Wandel der Sozialstruktur. Die gesellschaftlichen Herausforderungen und die Strategien der sozialen Gruppen* (Springer, 1998), 102.

⁴⁵ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, *Ibid.*, 219ff.

⁴⁶ Hempelmann, *Gott im Milieu*, 123.

⁴⁷ Franz Grubauer, „Zweierlei Logik. Milieus und Kirchenreform: Richtige Analyse, falsche Strategie?“ in *Zeitzeichen* (2/2012): 48–50.

⁴⁸ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, *Ibid.*, 247.

⁴⁹ Volkhard Krech, Soziologische Aspekte. *Reformspielräume in der Kirche: Ortsgemeinde und Regionalstrukturen am Beispiel der Evangelisch-lutherischen Landeskirche in Braunschweig*. Vol. 43. (Heidelberg: FEST, 1997), 33.

⁵⁰ Schulz, Hauschild, Kohler, *Ibid.*, 264-265.

⁵¹ *Ibid.*, 279.

⁵² *Ibid.*, 280.

⁵³ Hempelmann, *Kirche im Milieu*, 63.